

THE IMPLEMENTATION OF INTENSIVE AND EXTENSIVE READING IN IMPROVING TEACHING READING COMPREHENSION TO THE ADULT READER

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ingliz tilini o'rganish jarayoni, ayniqsa, o'qish ko'nikmasi haqida so'z boradi. Oliy ta'limda an'anaviy ta'lim usullarining cheklovlari, ular talabalarning qiziqish va motivatsiyasining pasayishiga olib kelishi ta'kidlanadi. Maqola talabalar oldingi bilimlarini hisobga olish va ijodiy o'qitish usullarini qo'llash muhimligini ko'rsatadi. Maqolada intensiv o'qish va keng qamrovli o'qish usullari taqqoslanib, ularning xususiyatlari va o'qish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishdagi roli yoritilgan. Intensiv o'qish qisqa va murakkab matnlarni chuqur tushunishga yo'naltirilgan bo'lsa, keng qamrovli o'qish oson matnlarni ko'p va zavq bilan o'qishga undaydi. Ushbu yondashuvlarning uyg'unligi talabalarning ingliz tilini o'qish ko'nikmalarini va motivatsiyasini yaxshilashda samarali ekanligi ta'kidlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: Ingliz tilini o'rganish, o'qishni tushunish, intensiv o'qish, keng qamrovli o'qish, qabul qiluvchi ko'nikmalar, ta'lim usullari, oliy ta'lim, talabalar motivatsiyasi, til o'zlashtirish.

Annotation: This article discusses the process of learning English with a focus on reading skills, which are part of receptive skills involving both the eyes and the brain. It highlights the limitations of traditional teaching methods in higher education, which often result in students' lack of interest and motivation. The article emphasizes the importance of incorporating students' prior knowledge and using creative teaching methods to improve reading comprehension. Two main methods, Intensive Reading (IR) and Extensive Reading (ER), are explored, comparing their characteristics, advantages, and roles in enhancing reading skills. IR focuses on detailed understanding of short, complex texts, while ER encourages reading large amounts of easy texts for enjoyment and fluency. The study underscores that combining both approaches effectively can improve students' reading comprehension and motivation in English learning.

Keywords: English learning, reading comprehension, intensive reading, extensive reading, receptive skills, teaching methods, higher education, student motivation, language acquisition.

The process of learning English includes four skills namely listening, speaking, reading, and writing. Reading is a learning activity dominated by the eyes and brain, where eyes receive the message, and then the brain processes to obtain the meaning of the message received. Reading included in the receptive skill. Receptive skill is emphasis on active involvement of the student as a reader. In each session of the English class, the four English skills are combined into different topics.

There are a number of factors that influence students' success in understanding English text when reading is taught at the higher education level. Several causes, including both internal and environmental factors, may contribute to its occurrence.

In order to teach reading, the lecturer hands out a reading text with a fresh theme

and attempts to carry out the process of eliciting the general knowledge or prior knowledge of the students related to the theme by responding to questions or inquiring about those themes so that students have an opinion what will be discussed in progress. Students used their prior knowledge of the topics during the process to aid in their comprehension of the book. This approach places a strong emphasis on the lead-in phase, which involves piquing students' interest in the subject matter, getting them to guess what they will be reading, and inspiring them to read. The teacher's creativity is needed in determining the proper method of teaching reading comprehension to students. The method that can be applied to improving reading skills is Intensive Reading and Extensive Reading to produce satisfying output in learning. Intensive Reading (IR) and Extensive Reading (ER) theoretically have the advantage that continuously reviewing and testing in a number of studies in various places all over the world. If used properly during the learning process, Intensive reading and Extensive Reading can speed up the process of learning to read English text as well as increase reading comprehension¹. The way that extensive reading approaches reading instruction is considerably different from the way that intensive reading, a widely used conventional method does. Extensive reading is a different approach for teaching students how to understand English text. Extensive reading is thought of as an additional strategy, not as a replacement for intensive reading. Therefore, there should be studies to determine the extent of the ability to read English text students with the adoption of the IR and ER methods. This prompted the authors to conduct research with the title "Intensive Reading and Extensive Reading in Teaching Reading Comprehension". However many studies have been done in Intensive Reading (IR) and Extensive Reading (ER).

The implementation of intensive reading (IR) the method in a study entitled "teaching reading of narrative text by using intensive reading". N. Dani stated that the score of student achievement in reading comprehension was in line with the development of their reading interest, it proved that the IR greatly assists students to understand the text starting from an easy passage up to an advanced reading level². Intensive reading (IR) can overcome obstacles encountered by teachers and students while most importantly students can read the text easily and have fun. Based on the empirical results, it concluded that IR and ER methods could be applied in English subjects to improve students' comprehension in reading English text. Extensive reading is reading widely and in large quantities, with the main aim to enjoy

¹Pigada, M. and Norbert S. Vocabulary Acquisition from Extensive Reading: A Case Study. *Reading in a Foreign Language*, 18(1). 2006-y.

² Dani, N. H, Muayanah, M. & Andayani E.A. Teaching Reading of Narrative Text by Using Intensive Reading. *English Education Department Journal*. 2008-y. P. 12.

reading activities, while intensive reading is reading that is only limited to the short text and carried out with the aim of understanding the whole content of reading. As an approach to reading literacy, these two methods are differentiated in various aspects relating to reading activities, which include the main objectives of reading, focus on reading text, the sources, and types of reading, the number of reading texts, the speed of reading level, and the method of reading. R. Day provides an excellent illustration of the traits of ER and IR approaches in Table 2.1.

<i>Types of reading</i>	<i>Intensive</i>	<i>Extensive</i>
Class goal (general purpose)	<i>Read accurately</i> (reading as accurately as possible)	<i>Read fluently</i> (reading as smoothly as possible)
Reading purpose (aim)	- <i>Translate</i> - <i>Answer questions</i>	- <i>Get/obtain information – Enjoy</i>
Focus (attention)	<i>Word by word</i>	<i>Meaning</i>
Material (reading material)	- <i>Often difficult</i> - <i>Lecturer's choice</i> (determined by the teachers)	- <i>Easy</i> - <i>Student's choice</i> (chosen by each students)
Amount (quantity)	<i>Not much</i>	<i>A lot</i>
Speed	<i>Slower</i> (a bit slow)	<i>Faster</i> (above normal speed)
Method (way)	- <i>Use dictionary</i> (use the dictionary as often as possible)	- <i>Minimum use of dictionary</i> (dictionary occasionally used)

Table 2.1 Characteristics of extensive reading and intensive reading.

Extensive reading (ER), based on Table 2.1, seems to be a quite different strategy from one that provides a fresh technique to educate the ability to read English literature. The improvement in reading comprehension of English text by using IR in the classroom is not very noticeable. Only when required by their instructors did the pupils read. The children hardly ever, if at all, read outside of the classroom.

According to R. Day and R. Harsch, the condition in reading classes clearly summarized in three circumstances. First, students have no willingness to read, or if they read they do it slowly and without enthusiasm (students have almost no desire to read, even if they read, it was done very slowly and less enthusiastically). Second, students come to the class with uneasy feelings, and they quickly intervening become bored with the reading lessons (students attending reading subjects with an uncomfortable mood, they are anxious, and very quickly get bored with reading class). Third, students only read English written materials if they are asked by their lecturer; apart from that, they rarely read English texts (students only read English text if it is instructed by their lecturer, beyond that they almost never read)³.

R. Day and R. Harsch concluded that the real portrait of teaching reading that applying a conventional approach (intensive reading) indicates three things:

³Day, R and Harsh R. . Extending extensive reading. reading in a foreign language, 27 (2). 2015-y.P. 294–301.

1. *Students who are learning to read in English do not actually read English text;*
2. *Students do not like reading;*
3. *Students rarely read.*

The benefits of the ER method include the fact that it can have a good impact on language learners' abilities as well as the fact that it is a very adaptable method that can be used with English learners of any proficiency level. M. Renandya's research, which focused on ER application for adult learners, demonstrated that ER had a favorable impact on raising learning quality. S. Shancke analyzed two research he conducted to look at the impact of ER on language acquisition in relation to the timing element. Both studies—conducted in 1986 and 1995—found that the ER program, which was put into place in just four months, significantly improved students' ability to learn the English language. This demonstrates that ER may be used with young children, adolescents, and adults, and that it can be applied to learning or studying in the short, medium, and long terms.

In general, successful IR and ER programs adopt the fundamental traits of IR and ER techniques for teaching English. The following ten traits should manifest, in accordance with R. Day and S. Bamford in Miller, in order to develop an effective emergency room program: The objectives of reading activities are for enjoyment, informational purposes, and general comprehension. Students should read reading materials as frequently as they can, and the material should be supplied in a variety of topics, types, and degrees of difficulty. The rewards earned from reading the text are the pleasure and satisfaction of reading activities itself, the level of difficulty from reading text must be similar to the level of students' reading comprehension, reading is done per student, and in silent reading, reading speed is fast rather than slow speed of reading, lecturer guides students to the aims of the reading activities, explain the methodology, keep record and track what each student reads, and help students to acquire the benefits of reading, and the lecturer should set a good example as an active and extensive reader.

Apart from extensive reading, intensive reading has the feel of an educational speech activity because either it may be done in a classroom with a teacher present or at home with the textbook author, who has created a unique approach for its (reading) development. Understanding is the end objective of intensive reading (as it is with extensive reading), but the level of comprehension is very different from that of extensive reading. Intensive reading texts require complete comprehension of both the topic and linguistic structure. Methodologists suggest short texts (1-2 pages) for teaching intensive reading, which can be read in one or two lessons or within one or two homework assignments, and for extensive - quite long texts (15-30 pages), intended for independent reading, keeping in mind that as the length of the material being read

increases, the process of its detailed understanding becomes more complicated. While not necessary, entertaining texts designed for in-depth reading are preferred. Relevance of the text's substance and linguistic components, as well as compatibility with the student's professional interests, are essential requirements.

A high degree of comprehension completion, a limited volume, low pace (indicated by the necessity to look up unfamiliar terminology in a dictionary), and originality of the material are the requirements for intensive reading. The primary criterion is still thought to be the criterion for differentiating between the completeness and depth of knowledge of the content being read, even if offering a description of both types of reading typically involves analyzing the entire range of offered criteria. This distinction causes the criteria to change into the target situation, wherein considerable reading is meant to achieve fluent (but rather superficial and frequently casual) possession.